

Trivalent Metal Complexes of Pentadentate Ligands

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The complexes of trivalent metals—chromium, manganese, iron and cobalt of two pentadentate ligands, 2,6-dipicolinic acid hydrazide (DPH) and N,N'-dibenzylidene dipicolinic acid hydrazide (DBPH) have been described. These complexes have been characterised by their elemental analysis and by molar conductance, electronic, infrared spectral (conventional and far i. r.) and magnetic susceptibilities measurements. Two types of complexes are isolated, (a) the first type includes the complexes of DPH which may be formulated as $[M(DPH)_2]X_3$, and (b) the complexes of DBPH which have a general formula of the type $[M(DBPH)]X_3$, where $M = Cr(III), Mn(III), Fe(III)$ or $Co(III)$, $X = Cl, NO_3$ or OAc . In the case of cobalt complexes X of coordination sphere is OH . The first type of complexes are six-coordinate, while the complexes of DBPH are five-coordinate, as it has been shown by infrared spectra that both the ligands, DPH and DBPH, act as pentadentate, having coordination sites at pyridine-nitrogen, amide-oxygen and hydrazinic nitrogen atoms. The quinquedentate nature of the ligand is confirmed by far infrared spectra where characteristic bands of $\nu(M-py)$, $\nu(M-N)$ and $\nu(M-O)$ vibrations are assigned. The various ligand field parameters (Dq, Ds , and Dt) have been calculated in conjunction with Racah interelectronic repulsion parameters B and C . In the case of chromium and manganese complexes, the use of Normalised Spherical Harmonic (NSH) Hamiltonian theory has been made to evaluate various parameters DQ, DS and DT . The degree of distortion of chromium and manganese complexes calculated in terms of DT/DQ lie in the range 0.17-0.18 and 0.34, respectively, indicating that in chromium complexes the metal atom is slightly above the basal plane of the square pyramid, while in the case of manganese complexes the displacement of metal is appreciable. The severe distorted nature of manganese complexes is probably due to the operation of Jahn-Teller effect, in addition to inequivalence of the donor atoms present in the ligands.

THE coordination chemistry of trivalent metal ions—chromium, manganese, iron and cobalt, involving higher multidentate ligands, particularly quinquedentate, has received limited attention. To date, only one report dealing with the structural investigations of the complexes of iron(III) with linear pentadentate ligands, is available¹. However, the complexes of these metal ions with macrocyclic pentadentate ligands have been the subject of intensive studies in recent years². Curiously enough, almost all the linear pentadentate ligands reported so far are dinegatively charged Schiff bases derived from salicylaldehydes or mercapto salicylaldehydes and polyamines³, with very few exceptions⁴. Recently, a series of papers⁵ describing complexes of first, second and third transition series metals of pentadentate ligands capable of giving rise to five-coordinate ionic species, have been reported from these laboratories.

In the present paper, we wish to report the synthesis of two pentadentate ligands, 2,6-dipicolinic acid hydrazide (DPH) and N, N'-dibenzylidene dipicolinic acid hydrazide (DBPH) and their complexes with trivalent chromium, manganese, iron and cobalt. The complexes are characterised by elemental analyses, and by molar conductance, electronic, infrared (conventional and far i. r.) spectral and magnetic susceptibility measurements. The structures of the ligands DPH and DBPH may be

depicted as follows :

Experimental

Materials : Dimethyl ester of dipicolinic acid was procured from Midland Yorkshire Tar Distillers Ltd., U.K. Manganese(III) acetate dihydrate was prepared by the method of Christensen⁶. All other chemicals used were of reagent grade.

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Synthesis of ligands : The ligands 2, 6-dipicolinic acid (DPH) and N, N'-dibenzylidene dipicolinic acid hydrazide (DBPH) have been synthesised by the methods given in literature⁷.

Preparation and isolation of complexes : A general procedure was adopted to synthesise the complexes of chromium, manganese and iron.

The stoichiometric amounts (50%) of the appropriate metal salts were taken in ethanol and mixed. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water bath for two hours followed by its concentration to half of the volume of the mixture when the precipitate of the complex was obtained. The precipitate was filtered, washed thoroughly with ethanol and water before drying at $\sim 85^\circ\text{C}$ in an oven. Yield $\sim 85\%$.

The manganese complexes were prepared in methanol. The complexes of cobalt were synthesised by the following procedure.

Cobalt chloride hexahydrate (2.0 mmole) dissolved in sufficient quantity of ethanol was mixed with the refluxing ethanolic solution of the ligand (2.0 mmole) and pH of the mixture was raised to 8.5 by adding a dilute solution of sodium hydroxide. A stream of air was passed into the mixture for about twenty hours to oxidise cobalt(II) into cobalt(III) species. The dark brown precipitate so obtained was filtered, washed successively with ethanol and water. The complexes were dried $\sim 85^\circ$ in an oven. Yield $\sim 75\%$.

Physical measurements and elemental analysis : Details of physical measurements, elemental analysis of C, H & N are same as described earlier⁵. The metal and halide estimations were carried out by EDTA titrations⁸ and Volhard's method, respectively. Nitrate was determined as its nitron salt⁹.

Results and Discussion

The complexes are soluble in ethanol and acetone. They are air stable both in solution and solid state. The molar conductance data reveal that complexes of DPH with all these metals but for Mn are uni-bivalent, while the complexes of DBPH are uni-trivalent electrolytes¹⁰. Accordingly, these classes of the complexes may be represented by the general formula of the types $[\text{M}(\text{DPH})\text{X}]_2\text{X}_2$ and $[\text{M}(\text{DBPH})\text{X}]_3$, where $\text{M} = \text{Cr(III)}, \text{Mn(III)}, \text{Fe(III)}$ or Co(III) , $\text{X} = \text{Cl}$ or NO_3 and in the case of cobalt complexes $\text{X} = \text{OH}$ (of coordination sphere only). These formulations are further supported by infrared spectra.

Infrared spectra : The infrared spectra of the ligands have not been reported, but studies on similar compounds are available¹¹. The present assignments are based on these studies.

The ligands, dipicolinic acid hydrazide and N, N'-dibenzylidene dipicolinic acid hydrazide are basically 2, 2'-disubstituted pyridine derivatives. A number of correlations have been made for such type of compounds¹¹. The vibrations generally affected¹² on

pyridine-nitrogen coordination to metal ions are the four $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ bands observed between 1450 and 1610 cm^{-1} , the ring-breathing mode 990 cm^{-1} , a skeletal mode around 740 cm^{-1} and an out-of-plane C-C deformation vibration 410 cm^{-1} .

The four $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$, $\nu(\text{C}=\text{N})$ bands are found ~ 1580 , 1500, 1505 and 1440 cm^{-1} in the spectra of the ligands. The 1580 cm^{-1} band shows an upward shift (10-15 cm^{-1}) in the spectra of the complexes. The ring-breathing band 990 cm^{-1} is replaced by a new band ~ 1020 cm^{-1} . Two strong bands in the spectra of the ligands ~ 790 and 730 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu(\text{C-H})$ and $\rho(\text{C-C})$ vibrational modes¹³, respectively. On complexation, the latter band splits into two components lying between 720 and 760 cm^{-1} , while the 790 cm^{-1} band appears as a broad band 800-810 cm^{-1} . The 410 cm^{-1} band also shifts towards higher frequencies (~ 430 cm^{-1}). All these changes in the vibrations of the pyridine ring indicate metal-pyridine coordination^{12, 14}. The magnitudes of 'shifts' though small, are meaningful. It may be interpreted in terms of weak coordination of pyridine nitrogen to a metal atom¹⁵.

Amide group vibrations : An amide group can coordinate either through nitrogen or oxygen atom depending upon the experimental conditions. The vibrations of interest in an amide group include¹⁶ amide I band (consists mainly of $\nu(\text{C}=\text{O})$ near 1680 cm^{-1} , amide II and III bands (arising from $\nu\text{CN} + \delta\text{NH}$) around 1520 and 1240 cm^{-1} , respectively; amide IV and VI bands near 690 and 480 cm^{-1} (originating from C=O out-of-plane and C=O in-plane deformation vibration modes, respectively)¹⁷. The free ligands exhibit characteristic bands around 1690, 1520 and 1260 cm^{-1} , assignable to amide I, II and III bands, respectively. In the spectra of complexes, amide I band shifts to lower frequencies (1640-1650 cm^{-1}), while amide II band increases in frequency (1535-1540 cm^{-1}) and amide III band splits into two components appearing between 1200-1210 and 1380-1388 cm^{-1} , respectively. The position of amide IV band remains unchanged, while the amide VI band shows an upward shift. These changes in the amide group vibrations reveal the coordination of the amide-oxygen to the metal ions¹⁶. The various changes occurring on amide-O coordination may be explained by assuming the decrease of the double bond character C=O group and the subsequent increase of the C-N double bond character¹⁸.

Hydrazinic and azomethine group vibrations : The spectrum of DPH contains sharp bands between 3300 and 3210 cm^{-1} , while two bands of medium intensity at 3200 and 3030 cm^{-1} are observed in the spectrum of DBPH. These bands may confidently be assigned to symmetric and asymmetric NH stretching vibrations, respectively. The bands appearing 980 cm^{-1} may be due to (NN) vibration modes. In addition to these bands, two bands at 1640 and 840 cm^{-1} (in the case of DPH only) appear which may be assigned to NH deformation coupled with OCN antisymmetric vibrations and NH out-of-plane bending modes¹⁹, respectively. In the spectra of the complexes of DPH the bands assigned to NH stretching vibrations exhibit a down-

ward shift and appears as a broad band between 3200 and 3030 cm^{-1} , the band at 1630 cm^{-1} disappears altogether and the NH out-of-plane bending band at 840 cm^{-1} diminishes appreciably in its intensity. All these changes show coordination of the hydrazinic nitrogen to the metal atoms. The changes in the NH vibration modes are a consequence of drainage of electrons from nitrogen atoms resulting in the weakening of N-H bond²⁰.

Strong absorptions between 1580-1630 cm^{-1} are usually associated with phenyl ring vibrations, but azomethine group ($>\text{C}=\text{N}$) may also be responsible for it, for conjugated systems containing both $\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ linkage often exhibit one or more strong bands between 1500 and 1700 cm^{-1} . It is usually not possible to identify such bands with particular $\text{C}=\text{C}$ or $\text{C}=\text{N}$ linkage. However, a stringent assignment of the ($>\text{C}=\text{N}-$) band can be made by comparing the spectra of the hydrazide and its benzylidene derivative. The spectra of DBPH show one strong band $\sim 1640 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ with a shoulder at $\sim 1630 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. These two vibrations may be assigned to symmetric and asymmetric stretching vibration modes of the azomethine linkage²¹. In the spectra of the complexes of DBPH, the 1640 cm^{-1} band shifts to lower range by 15-20 cm^{-1} . This lowering may be taken an indication of the azomethine nitrogen being coordinated to the metal atom. The 'shifts' are small, but it is expected in view of the stronger force present in the ($>\text{C}=\text{N}-$) bond²².

Far infrared spectra of the ligands and complexes : In the far infrared region, the bands appearing 610, 550, 450, 430 and 280 cm^{-1} are assigned to in-plane ring deformation, NH_2 -rocking, C-C out-of-plane deformation and C-C torsional modes¹¹, respectively. Some unassigned bands occur near 450, 350, 235, 228 and 204 cm^{-1} .

Several new bands appear in the spectra of the complexes. The bands appearing 250, 250, 252, and 265 cm^{-1} assigned to $\nu(\text{Cr-py})$, $\nu(\text{Mn-py})$, $\nu(\text{Fe-py})$ and $\nu(\text{Co-py})$ vibration modes²⁴, respectively. Similarly new bands appearing 370, 375, 372 and 380 cm^{-1} are due to $\nu(\text{Cr-O})$, $\nu(\text{Mn-O})$, $\nu(\text{Fe-O})$ and $\nu(\text{Co-O})$ vibrations²⁴, respectively. Some more new bands appear between 450 and 475 cm^{-1} . The bands 450, 470, 472 and 475 cm^{-1} are tentatively assigned to $\nu(\text{Cr-N})$, $\nu(\text{Mn-N})$, $\nu(\text{Fe-N})$ and $\nu(\text{Co-N})$ vibrations²², respectively. In the case of chromium and iron complexes strong bands observed ~ 340 and 260 cm^{-1} are assigned to $\nu(\text{Cr-Cl})$ and $\nu(\text{Fe-Cl})$, respectively. The $\nu(\text{M-Cl})$ bands are absent in the spectra of DBPH complexes of these metals. In the complex $[\text{Co}(\text{DPH})(\text{OH})]_2$, a distinct band observed at 515 cm^{-1} which is probably due to $\nu(\text{Co-OH})$ vibration mode.

Following conclusions are drawn on the basis of infrared spectral studies of the complexes: (a) both DPH and DBPH act as pentadentate ligands with all the metals studied herein and have sites of coordination at pyridine-nitrogen, amide-oxygen and hydrazinic or azomethine-nitrogen atoms, (b) both the side-chains are symmetrical, and (c) complexes of chromium, iron and

cobalt of DPH are six-coordinate while the complexes of DBPH with chromium through cobalt are five-coordinate. The complex $[\text{Mn}(\text{DPH})](\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$ also appears to be five-coordinate. It is probably due to its larger size that the acetate ion cannot enter the coordination sphere. The ligand DBPH appears to be more suitable for penta-coordination due to the presence of bulky phenyl groups in it, which prevent the entrance of sixth ligand to be attached to the metal ion. These contentions are further supported by the electronic spectra and magnetic susceptibility measurements of these complexes.

Electronic Spectral and Magnetic studies

Chromium complexes : The magnetic moments of the chromium complexes lie in the range 3.70-3.80 BM at room temperature (300°K) and are close to the predicted value of 3.87 BM for three unpaired electrons, irrespective of the five- or six-coordinate environment around the metal ion²⁵.

The complexes of DPH shows four bands ~ 1450 , ~ 17000 , 24500, and 34200 cm^{-1} . These bands are similar to those observed for six-coordinate chromium(III) complexes. Assuming the effective field around metal ion as D_{4h} , these bands can be assigned²¹ to ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^2\text{T}_{2g}({}^2\text{E}_g)$, ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{2g}$, ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{F})$ and ${}^4\text{A}_{2g} \rightarrow {}^4\text{T}_{1g}(\text{P})$ in the order of increasing energy. Various ligand field and nephelauxetic parameters 10Dq , β_{35} , and β_{55} are calculated²⁷ and given in Table 2. However, different types of spectra are obtained for DBPH complexes. These complexes show bands ~ 8200 , 13600, 18200, 21200, and 31250 cm^{-1} (chloride complex), 7000, 12500, 17500 and 30800 cm^{-1} (nitrate complex). These bands do not resemble those observed for six-coordinate octahedral or tetragonal complexes²⁸. However, the spectra can well be compared with the spectra of five-coordinate chromium(III) complexes²⁹.

The electronic spectra of Cr(III)-DBPH complexes in pyridine show bands ~ 7500 , 12500, 18000, 28000 and 31000 cm^{-1} . These bands resemble those of the reflectance spectra. Thus, it appears that these complexes are five-coordinate both in solution and the solid state.

Keeping in view the geometry and pentadentate nature of the ligands (vide infrared) and comparing the present spectra, it appears that the most probable geometry of the complexes is square pyramid. Considering the effective symmetry of the molecule as C_{4v} , the spectral bands ~ 13500 , ~ 18200 , 28200 and 30200 can be assigned²⁸ to ${}^4\text{B}_1 \rightarrow {}^4\text{E}({}^4\text{T}_{2g})$, ${}^4\text{B}_1 \rightarrow {}^4\text{B}_2$, ${}^4\text{B}_1 \rightarrow {}^4\text{A}_2$ and ${}^4\text{E}_1 \rightarrow {}^4\text{E}({}^4\text{T}_{1g})$, respectively. The assignments are based on the fact that selection rules pertaining to C_{4v} six-coordinate cis-complexes do not change for a five-coordinate square pyramidal geometry²⁸.

Manganese complexes : The magnetic moments of the complexes are in the range expected for high-spin d^4 system 4.85-4.92 BM. However, a small lowering of magnetic moment from spin-only value of 4.94 BM may arise from the effects of lowering of symmetry or spin-orbit coupling.

The electronic spectra of the complexes have several bands in the region 8000-40000 cm^{-1} . The bands $\sim 12200, \sim 15200$ and 20400 cm^{-1} are easily discernable and well defined. These spectral bands exclude octahedral stereochemistry for these complexes because the bands for such a geometry³¹ lie $\sim 14000, 17500, 19000, 24000$ and 35000 cm^{-1} . However, the spectra resemble well with the reported five-coordinate square pyramidal species of trivalent manganese³². The molecular models indicate that pyridine nucleus should be present on the axial position and other four donor atoms of the molecule form the basal plane of a square pyramid. Thus, assuming a square pyramidal geometry for these complexes, the bands $\sim 12200, 15200$ and 20400 cm^{-1} are assigned³² to ${}^6B_1 \rightarrow {}^6A_1, {}^6B_1 \rightarrow {}^6B_2$, and ${}^6B \rightarrow {}^6E$, respectively. Alternatively, the spectral bands can be assigned in terms of single electron transitions as $d_{x^2} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$, (12200 cm^{-1}), $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ (15200 cm^{-1}) and $d_{xz}, d_{yz} \rightarrow d_{x^2-y^2}$ (20400 cm^{-1}). These assignments are parallel to those made by Marianelli *et al.* for high-spin square pyramidal manganese(III) complexes of porphyrins³³. The degree of tetragonal distortion can be calculated in terms of DT/DQ, by the application of Normalised Spherical Harmonic (NSH) Hamiltonian Theory developed by Lever *et al.*³⁴. The degree of distortion for DPH and DBPH complexes of manganese(III) is 0.34 which is quite close to 0.4225, the limiting value postulated for square planar complexes³⁴. Thus, the manganese complexes are severely distorted (tetragonally) and chief cause of distortion appears to be operation of Jahn-Teller effect in addition to inequivalence of the donor atoms.

Iron complexes: The magnetic moments of iron complexes lie in the range 5.84-5.90 BM at room temperature (295°K). These values are in the range expected for high-spin d^5 systems, 5.80-6.00 BM.

The electronic spectra of the complex of DPH shows bands around 17500, 19200, 24800 and 28500 cm^{-1} .

The bands resemble those of high-spin six-coordinate iron(III) complexes and the first three bands may be assigned³⁵ to ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (4D), ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}$ (4A_2) and ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}$ in the order of increasing energy. The 28500 cm^{-1} band is due to charge-transfer phenomenon. The bands observed ~ 17500 and 24900 cm^{-1} appear to be split of the first band. Thus, it appears that the complex has a distorted octahedral geometry.

The electronic spectra of the complex $[\text{Fe}(\text{DBPH})]\text{Cl}_3$ show bands in the regions $\sim 7500, 9800$ (15400 and 2700) cm^{-1} . These bands are not consistent with either octahedral or tetrahedral geometry of trivalent iron complexes³. However, these bands are similar to those observed for high-spin five-coordinate iron(III) complex³⁶. On the basis of similar reasons as advanced in the case of chromium-DBPH complex, this iron(III) complex also appears to have square pyramidal geometry. Thus iron(III) complex also appears to have square pyramidal geometry. Thus assuming the effective symmetry of the complex as C_{4v} , the bands ~ 7500 and 9800 cm^{-1} may be assigned³⁶ to $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{xz}, d_{yz}$ and $d_{xy} \rightarrow d_{z^2}$, respectively. Alternatively, both the transitions may terminate in ($x^2 - y^2$) level from Z^2 and (xz, yz) levels. Any attempt to make accurate assignments is, however, difficult due to the likelihood of interaction of the metal-ligand system lifting the degeneracy of the d_{xz}, d_{yz} level.

Cobalt complexes: Both the cobalt(III) complexes are diamagnetic in nature. The electronic spectra of $[\text{Co}(\text{DPH})(\text{OH})]\text{Cl}_2$ show bands $\sim 19200, 22400$ and 29400 cm^{-1} . The spectra can be interpreted in terms of the pseudo-octahedral symmetry of cobalt complex. Accordingly, the first two bands can be assigned³⁷ to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1E_{1g}$ and ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1A_{2g}$ in the order of increasing energy. The higher energy band (29400 cm^{-1}) which appear as shoulder may be assigned to ${}^1A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^1T_{2g}$.

TABLE I - ANALYTICAL DATA

Complex	Colour	Calculated % of					Found % of				
		C	H	N	X	M	C	H	N	X	M
$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}_6\text{O}_2)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Light violet	21.56	3.33	17.97	27.34	13.34	21.71	3.22	18.18	27.60	13.26
$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}_6\text{O}_2)(\text{NO}_3)](\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Sky blue	17.91	2.77	23.88	39.65	11.08	17.75	2.71	24.05	40.12	11.01
$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2)]\text{Cl}_2$	Violet	47.59	3.21	13.22	20.11	9.81	47.45	3.32	13.18	20.25	9.90
$[\text{Cr}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2)](\text{NO}_3)_2$	Violet	41.37	2.79	16.09	30.54	8.53	41.82	2.92	15.85	30.01	8.24
$[\text{Mn}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}_6\text{O}_2)](\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Yellow	33.69	4.75	15.12	—	11.86	33.32	4.68	15.05	—	11.72
$[\text{Mn}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2)](\text{CH}_3\text{COO})_2$	Yellow	41.79	4.31	11.60	—	9.11	42.10	4.12	11.75	—	9.52
$[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}_6\text{O}_2)\text{Cl}]\text{Cl}_2$	Dark green	23.50	2.51	19.58	29.80	15.62	23.72	2.41	19.72	29.58	15.52
$[\text{Fe}(\text{C}_8\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2)]\text{Cl}_2$	Green	47.29	3.19	13.13	19.89	10.49	48.10	3.32	13.24	19.96	10.59
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_7\text{H}_9\text{N}_6\text{O}_2)(\text{OH})]\text{Cl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$	Dark brown	21.18	3.27	17.65	26.86	14.86	20.98	3.12	17.58	27.03	14.68
$[\text{Co}(\text{C}_{11}\text{H}_{17}\text{N}_6\text{O}_2)]\text{Cl}_2$	Brown	46.97	3.16	13.04	19.85	10.98	47.25	3.13	13.11	20.22	11.10

TABLE 2—ELECTRONIC SPECTRAL AND MAGNETIC DATA

Complex	Bands	Assignments	10Dq cm ⁻¹	β_{as}	β_{ss}	DQ	DT	DQ/DT	$\mu_{eff}/B.M.(300^\circ K)$
[Cr(DPH)Cl]Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	13200	⁴ A _{2g} → ² E _g	17250	0.48	0.77	—	—	—	3.70
	17250	→ ⁴ T _{2g} (F)							
	21260	→ ⁴ T _{1g} (F)							
	37250	→ ⁴ T _{1g} (P)							
[Cr(DPH)(NO ₂)(NO ₃) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	13180	⁴ A _{2g} → ² E _g	17300	0.47	0.78	—	—	—	3.80
	17300	→ ⁴ T _{2g} (F)							
	21250	→ ⁴ T _{1g} (F)							
	37300	→ ⁴ T _{1g} (P)							
	8300	⁴ B ₁ → ⁴ E _a							
13500									
18250	→ ⁴ B ₂								
28250	→ ⁴ A ₂								
30000	→ ⁴ E _b	18180	—	—	41570	7020	0.18	3.72	
[Cr(DBPH)](NO ₂) ₂	8270								→ ⁴ E _a
	13620								⁴ B ₁ → ⁴ E _a
	18180								
	27170								
31250	→ ⁴ E _b								
[Mn(DPH)](CH ₃ COO) ₂ ·2H ₂ O	12200	⁶ B ₁ → ⁶ A ₁	15200	—	—	37930	12850	0.34	4.92
	15210	→ ⁶ B ₂							
	20400	→ ⁶ E							
	24000	C.T.							
[Mn(DBPH)](CH ₃ COO) ₂	12250	⁶ B ₁ → ⁶ A ₁	15300	—	—	37800	12800	0.34	4.85
	15300	→ ⁶ B ₂							
	20250	→ ⁶ E							
	23950	C.T.							
	7500	^{d_{xy}} → ^{d_{xx}} , ^{d_{yy}} , ^{d_{zz}}							
9800	15400		—	—	—	—	—	5.84	
7450		^{d_{xy}} → ^{d_{xx}} , ^{d_{yy}} , ^{d_{zz}}							
9820	15250		—	—	—	—	—	—	5.90
[Co(DPH)(OH)]Cl ₂ ·2H ₂ O	16150	¹ A _{1g} → ¹ E _g	21690	—	—	—	—	—	Diamag.
20200	→ ¹ A _{2g}								
29590	→ ¹ T _{2g}								
[Co(DBPH)]Cl ₂	15000	Charge Transfer	—	—	—	—	—	—	Diamag.
	23000								
	30000								
	37000								

The pseudo-octahedral geometry can either have a cis-form (C_{4v} symmetry) or a trans form in accordance with D_{4h} symmetry. The shape of molecular models suggests that the trans-form (D_{4h}) is more favourable for this complex. Thus by assuming the effective field around the metal ion as D_{4h}, the various ligand field parameters in conjunction with Racah inter-electronic repulsion parameters (B and C) are calculated using the equations²⁷: E(¹A_{1g} → ¹A_{2g}) = 10 D_{q-c}; E(¹A_{1g} → ¹E_g) = 10Dq - ³/₅ Dt - C; and E(¹A_{1g} - ¹T_{2g}) = 10Dq + 16 B - C. The values obtained for different parameters are given in Table 2. These values are compatible with the pseudo-octahedral geometry of the complex.²⁷

The electronic spectra of the DBPH complex show bands ~ 8300, 16700, 17800, 22900, 29450 and 37000 cm⁻¹. Out of these five bands, the bands appearing ~16700 and 17800 cm⁻¹ are characteristic of six-coordinate octahedral cobalt(III) complexes. The band ~22900 cm⁻¹ is too low to be assigned to charge-transfer transition; the bands ~29450 and 37000 cm⁻¹ can be charge-transfer of the type²⁷ σ-P → d. Thus the

electronic spectra indicate the presence of some unusual species. The appearance of a band ~22900 cm⁻¹ support the penta-coordination²⁸ around the metal ion which is also indicated by the infrared spectra of the complex.

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